

Effects of *Bemisia tabaci* and *Macrolophus pygmaeus* on morphophysiological traits of plants

Whitefly, Predator, Zoophytophagy, Trophic interactions, Plant morphology

Italy

Whiteflies (*Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae*) are critical pests attacking many cultivated plants worldwide. Among them, *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) is a global pest causing significant losses to a wide variety of crops by affecting plant development. To control *B. tabaci* infestations, the release of natural enemies has become increasingly important as an ecologically safe and effective biological control method, with the mirid bug *Macrolophus pygmaeus* (Rambur) playing a primary role.

However, due to its zoophytophagous habits, an improper application rate of this predator can also make it a threat to plants. Therefore, a better understanding of the role that *M. pygmaeus* plays in crops is needed. To address this, a study was conducted to assess the impact of whiteflies alone or combined with *M. pygmaeus* on vegetable solanaceous crops, with special emphasis on tomato and eggplant.

The main morphological (total height, dry weights, leaf area) and physiological (photosynthetic performance, indirect chlorophyll content) parameters of the plants were analyzed in different conditions (healthy plants, or infested by the pest, or with pest and predator together). At the experimental conditions and the insect densities adopted, results show a variable susceptibility by different plant species to *B. tabaci* and a significant reduction induced by *M. pygmaeus* in negative effects caused by the pest on morphophysiological traits of the plants.

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NKB: Guadalupe López

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virtigation

The European project “Virtigation”: an opportunity to learn more about whitefly pests of vegetable crops and to update on strategies for their

Whiteflies, Vectors, Viruses, Tomato, Cucurbits

Italy

The project VIRTIGATION, funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 programme, involves 25 partners from 12 different countries, and aims to develop solutions for the control of emerging viruses on cucurbits and tomatoes caused by begomoviruses and tobamoviruses (the first ones transmitted by insects). Main entomological objectives of the project are to:

- i) understand plant-virus-vector interactions;
- ii) identify ecological factors that favour outbreaks of infections;
- iii) investigate biology of vector insects and their virus transmission efficiency under climate change conditions;
- iv) enhance and optimize natural resistance, especially for lower attractiveness of plants to vector insects;
- v) develop solutions for the integrated control of the viruses and their vectors.

Within this project, the University of Catania (Department of Agriculture, Food and Environment - DiBA) will have to:

- a) contribute to a survey in various partner countries on methods used for whitefly control, especially *Bemisia tabaci*;
- b) coordinate field trials to evaluate the efficacy of new plant extracts with insecticidal action, also analysing their secondary effects on natural enemies and pollinators;
- c) carry out field trials with the most promising accessions for their resistance to *B. tabaci* MED;
- d) evaluate the combination of different approaches for whitefly control.

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virtigation

Impact of climate change on a whitefly-transmitted virus

Bemisia tabaci, Tomato Leaf Curl New Delhi Virus (ToLCNDV), Epidemiology, Climate change

Luxembourg

Bemisia tabaci (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) is a significant pest worldwide, causing damage to plants both directly and indirectly by transmitting numerous economically important viruses. The **Tomato Leaf Curl New Delhi Virus (ToLCNDV)**, transmitted by whiteflies from the *Bemisia tabaci* complex, spread from Southeast Asia to the Mediterranean region in the early 2000s. ToLCNDV affects **cucurbits** and has caused significant economic losses in Europe, particularly in Greece, Italy, Spain, Portugal, and recently in France. **Climate change** is expected to exacerbate the spread of *B. tabaci* and its associated diseases. To better understand how climate change will affect the epidemiology of ToLCNDV in cucurbits, LIST researchers are testing how changes in temperature, humidity, and CO₂ concentration in climatic chambers will affect the acquisition and inoculation of ToLCNDV in *B. tabaci*, as well as the gene expression of target genes in the whitefly vector. The experiments aim to shed light on an unexplored topic and help address future challenges in plant protection.

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Matteo Ripamonti, Michael Eickermann, Jürgen Junk

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virtigation

VIRTIGATION: A NETWORK TO FIGHT VIRAL DISEASES

Virtigation, Tomatoes, Cucurbits, Emerging viral diseases, Bio-based solutions

Germany

"**VIRTIGATION** is a multi-actor project on a mission to protect **tomatoes** and **cucurbits** in Northern Europe and the Mediterranean Basin. Together with partners from key EU neighbouring areas - **Morocco, Israel** and **India** - the VIRTIGATION project aims to develop a set of **bio-based solutions** to safeguard tomatoes and cucurbits from emerging viral diseases.

Specifically, **VIRTIGATION** addresses emerging viral diseases caused by the begomovirus **ToLCNDV (Tomato leaf curl New Delhi Virus**, transmitted by whiteflies) and the tobamovirus **ToBRFV (Tomato brown rugose fruit virus**, mechanically transmitted). In particular **practice-relevant measures** will be developed to protect these plants."

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